

Global Best Practices in Civil – Military Cooperation and the Regional Case Studies

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Abstract:

This paper examines the global best practices in civil-military cooperation. It contends that *civil-military cooperation* (CIMIC) also called *civil-military relations* (CIMIR) plays a pivotal role in enhancing the efficiency of operations of military personnel in conflict zones, disaster relief scenarios, and peace-building efforts, focusing on strategies that foster collaboration between military and civilian actors to achieve common objectives. Effective CIMIC involves clear communication, shared goals, and mutual respect, allowing for seamless coordination in complex environments. International frameworks like UN's Guidelines and NATO's crisis management approach prioritize civilian needs while leveraging military capabilities. Key practices include community integration, technology sharing, joint planning, and flexible command structures. This paper explores case studies from the Middle East, Africa, and Southeast Asia to demonstrate the importance of context-specific approaches that respect local cultures and governance structures. Challenges such as balancing security concerns with humanitarian needs, maintaining operational efficiency, and ensuring accountability are addressed through continuous dialogue, training, and evaluation. The implementation of these best practices can significantly improve outcomes in complex environments, facilitating the provision of security, humanitarian aid, and development in post-conflict and disaster situations. The paper is qualitative in nature and utilizes secondary data from textbooks, journal articles and other archival materials.

Keywords: Africa, Conflicts, Middle-East, Military, CIMIC, global best practices, Southeast Asia.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The introduction of civil-military cooperation (CIMIC), both in theory and in practice, in managing conflicts, especially in the post-Cold War era, becomes necessary given the dynamism and complexity that most of these conflicts have assumed. Indeed, as Agata Mazurkiewicz has rightly observed, “contemporary military missions are conducted in complex political and social contexts, where the area of operation is shared by armed forces with various civilian actors such as civilian organizations, indigenous populations, and local authorities (Mazurkiewicz, 2022: 1).

Further arguing, Mazurkiewicz asserts that this characteristic of the operational environment has propelled international organizations such as the North Atlantic Treaty Alliance (NATO), the United Nations (UN), and the European Union (EU), as well as individual states, to establish specific military functions, which facilitate communication and cooperation between the military force and civilian actors. The end of the bipolar world order vis-à-vis the Cold War era between the late 1980s and early 1990s did not only subject the geopolitical situation to undergo significant changes but also heralded the intervention of the international community in internal conflicts that permeated across many countries of the world, especially in places like Bosnia, Kosovo, and East Timor, including several parts of Africa, Asia, and the Middle East at an alarming rate. With the prevalence of such a new normal within the global community, global intervention response to this upsurge in conflicts incidentally resulted in increased contact between international intervention troops and humanitarian aid providers.

To put an end to many of these conflicts with several humanitarian catastrophes and guarantee peace and stability with the view to encourage peace-building efforts and, to some extent, a responsibility to protect vulnerable citizens, there is an obvious need for these actors, both the intervening international armed forces and humanitarian aid actors, to work more closely together for their mutual interest. Therefore, the interaction and/or contact that exist between the peacekeeping or peace-enforcing troops and civil humanitarian aid actors in conflict situations in any given society rightly explain the concept of Civil-Military Cooperation (CIMIC). In a nutshell, CIMIC subsequently becomes a key policy and operational issue for all involved actors. It is worthwhile to note that various actors hold divergent perspectives on how to respond to the conflict

situations while recognizing the need to find ways of cooperation and coordination between and among them.

The notion of CIMIC further suggests that military action alone is insufficient to prevent or resolve conflict prevalent in any given place, as the success of any peace-management and peace-building effort operations requires enhanced interaction amongst both the military and non-military actors at all levels before, during, and after military operations.

Thus, this chapter is divided into five main sections. Besides the introduction, other sections are conceptualizing CIMIC, peacekeeping, and global best practices; typologies of civil-military relations and cooperation; CIMIC in the Middle East, Africa, and Southeast Asia case studies; challenges facing CIMIC; and conclusion.

2. CONCEPTUALIZING CIMIC, PEACEKEEPING AND GLOBAL BEST PRACTICES

2.1 Civil-Military Cooperation (CIMIC)

Since the early 1990s, CIMIC has been the controversial term of a heated debate within the civilian, humanitarian, and military community regarding their relationship with each other (Rehse, 2004: 14). The concept of CIMIC is difficult to define because over the years, it has been undergoing a paradigm shift as a result of the new security landscape emerging after the end of the Cold War (Kristoffersen, 2005: 5). Hence, it has been explained differently by many authors. The debate on it by several organizations and nation-states continued unabated. For example, according to the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO), CIMIC is defined as “the coordination and cooperation, in support of the mission, between the NATO Commander and civil actors, including national populations and local authorities, as well as international, national, and non-governmental organizations and agencies” (NATO, 2002; 2018). On the other hand, the UN simply views it as the need to cooperate at all levels within and outside the immediate area of the emergency by military forces and civil partners. To Peter Rehse, CIMIC, as used in the NGO community, refers to “military involvement in humanitarian aid” (Rehse, 2004: 13).

Ultimately, objectives of CIMIC in line with NATO’s perspective are to, among other things, (a) achieve greater coherence of efforts by different actors; (b) develop

mechanisms to optimize interactions; and (c) improve practical cooperation in order to collaborate more effectively in planning and conducting operations. Essentially, CIMIC becomes the effective and efficient management of complex conflict situations by both armed forces and civil partners alike (Trogu, 2025; Muthee, 2022).

However, for this paper, CIMIC implies a process where military forces and civilian actors cooperate to achieve mutually beneficial goals, especially during peacekeeping operations and disaster relief efforts. Therefore, it facilitates development, reconstruction, humanitarian aid, and legitimizes missions thereby promoting lasting peace and stability. Arising from this, information exchange, civil environment support, and humanitarian principles adherence, are major elements of CIMIC (Winslow, 1998).

2.2 Peacekeeping

In the view of Espen Barth Eide, “peacekeeping is no longer what it used to be” (Eide, 2001:1) (cited in Kristoffersen, 2005: 2). The question then is what did peacekeeping used to be, and what is it now? Kristoffersen (2005: 2) says the history of peacekeeping may be presented as different generations of peacekeeping. The first generation of peacekeeping occurred after the end of the Second World War. First-generation peacekeeping may also be labeled traditional peacekeeping, defined by Nissen (2002:7) as, “A traditional peacekeeping operation is composed of lightly armed military personnel deployed in a conflict area under a mandate of the UN Security Council and with the consent of the parties to the conflict. The peacekeeping force is to be impartial to the conflicting parties and base its activities on the principle of minimum use of force (self-protection)”.

However, the second generation of peacekeeping efforts in the post-Cold War era were mostly in intrastate conflicts. For instance, Peter Rehse opines that the majority of wars in the post-Cold War era quickly metamorphosed from inter-state conflicts to predominantly intra-state disputes and civil wars simply because the end of the Cold War created absence of external support among nations of the world (Rehse, 2004: 11).

Presently, peacekeeping operations have evolved into a third generation of peacekeeping, which, according to Dybwad (1999:7), is characterized by long-term peace and nation-building efforts and an expanded regional responsibility. In contemporary times, CIMIC has entered the scene as a crucial tool in dealing with the great number of players. The new peacekeeping has a substantial non-military mandate and composition

in addition to its military component. The ultimate objective for this new generation of peacekeeping operations around the world is to consolidate state structures by means of a repertoire of tasks conducted by a wide range of players. Examples of third-generation peacekeeping operations are the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) Monitoring Group (ECOMOG) peacekeeping missions in Liberia and Sierra Leone, the African Union-United Nations Hybrid Operation in Darfur (UNAMID), the Implementation Force (IFOR), and the Stabilization Force (SFOR) in the former Yugoslavia.

2.3 Typologies of Civil-Military Relations and Cooperation

From ancient Greece up to the end of the twentieth century, with displacement or the threat of the displacement of an elected government by overt military action, CIMIC has been a recurrent theme. Several works on civil-military relations and cooperation exist (Lasswell & Kaplan, 1950; Finer, 1962; Huntington, 1962; Janowitz, 1964; Stepan, 1974; Millet, 1979; Ujo, 1996; Karabelias, 1998; Eminue, 2006; Salaam & Usman, 2019; and Day and Khisa, 2022).

CIMIC can be classified into several types based on three distinctive goals, purpose, direction, and level of interaction, between military and civilian actors during military operations, peacekeeping missions, disaster response, or stabilization efforts. According to NATO doctrine and United Nations peacekeeping practices, the commonly recognized types of CIMIC are *mission support*, *humanitarian and development support*, *civil-military liaison*, *tactical and strategic CIMIC*, *reactive and proactive CIMIC*, and *integrated or comprehensive approach CIMIC* (NATO, 2003; UN OCHA, 2008; and Pirozzi, 2010).

On mission support (otherwise known as ‘support to the force’), civilian actors such as NGOs and local authorities, provide information, resources, or services that enhance the military’s operational effectiveness. The ultimate goal is to facilitate the mission’s success by leveraging local knowledge, infrastructure, or community support.

For the humanitarian and development support, which is also described as ‘support to the civil environment, the military provides assistance to the civilian population or institutions, especially where civilian capacity is limited. This is to ensure the stabilization of the environment, win local support, and address urgent needs like food, water, shelter, or medical care. The civil-military liaison establishes dialogue,

coordination, and information-sharing mechanisms between military forces and civilian actors with the aim of avoiding duplication, resolve conflicts, and synchronize efforts across civil and military sectors.

Tactical and strategic CIMIC is distinguished by the level of engagement. While tactical CIMIC is conducted at the field or operational level with focus on local population engagement, infrastructure projects, or immediate humanitarian assistance, strategic CIMIC involves high-level planning, policy alignment, and interaction with national governments, international organizations, or senior UN staff. It focuses on long-term goals such as state-building, governance, and development planning.

In the case of reactive and Proactive CIMIC, while the former responds to emergencies, such as natural disasters like an earthquake or urgent humanitarian crises requiring military response, proactive CIMIC is planned in advance to build resilience, strengthen civil institutions, and prevent conflict escalation.

The integrated or comprehensive approach CIMIC is concerned with coordinated and collaborative strategy that brings together military, civilian, governmental, non-governmental, and international actors to address complex crises such as conflicts, peacebuilding, or humanitarian emergencies in a holistic, coherent, and mutually reinforcing manner. This approach recognizes that security, development, governance, and humanitarian needs are interconnected, and effective responses require multi-sectoral coordination, not isolated action by the military or civilian actors alone.

2.4 Global Best Practices

In the context of CIMIC, global best practices refer to the widely recognized principles, norms, and institutional frameworks that guide the balanced, democratic, and accountable interaction between civilian authorities and the military. These practices are based on lessons learned across different countries and are intended to ensure that armed forces remain under civilian control, serve national interests, and respect democratic governance, human rights, and the rule of law. Thus, civilian control of the military, clear legal and constitutional framework, transparency and accountability, professionalism of the armed forces, respect for human rights and rule of law, civil-military dialogue and institutional mechanisms, and balanced defense policy, are identified to be the key

components of global best practices in CIMIC (Huntington, 1957; OECD, 2004; Bruneau & Matei, 2008; UN, 2008; and Croissant, Kuehn, Chambers & Wolf, 2010).

3. REGIONAL CASE STUDIES OF CIMIC IN THE MIDDLE EAST, AFRICA, AND SOUTHEAST ASIA

CIMIC in the selected regional case studies adhere to the global best practices. For example, just as in any given society, the military in the Middle East is one of the most powerful institutions, even when under the control of civilian officials. Hence, the military has been identified as a key institutional player regardless regime, in the setting and execution of government policy. In fact, the military forces have also played a central role in deciding the outcomes of protest movements and revolutions in countries affected by the Arab Spring (El Kurd, 2014). The cooperating roles of the Jordanian military in public health, refugee management, and border control with civilian oversight and cooperation in development helping the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan to weathered a number of political challenges inspired by the Arab Spring since early 2011 is worth noting.

Similarly, in Beirut, Lebanon, when almost 3,000 tons of ammonium nitrate exploded on August 4, 2020, it caused a humanitarian catastrophe that killed more than 200 people and wounded tens of thousands. The swift role of the military in delivering critical supplies saving lives cannot be over-emphasized (Garomone, 2020).

In Africa, a report suggested that the people trusted most of their militaries (African Defence Forum, ADF, 2014: 4). In a survey of residents of 19 African nations conducted by Gallup, a polling firm, 61 percent of respondents said they had confidence in the military as an institution, meaning that the military is more trusted than bankers, the health care sector, journalists, or national governments, making the bond forged between the armed forces and civilians unbreakable (ADF, 2014: 4). In fact, without civil-military trust, no national army can claim legitimacy, as history shows that militaries are most respected when they are subordinate to elected civilian officials, free of corruption, obedient to the rule of law, and responsive to the needs of citizens. However, the confidence of most Nigerians in their country has significantly dwindled. Perhaps, this is as a result of persistent rebellions of several terrorist groups, bandits, and kidnappers, for which the Nigerian army has not quelled. This further aided the perception of possible

collusion between the military and civilian politicians thereby necessitating the fight against terror into a profit-making venture.

In Southeast Asia, and particularly Thailand, civil-military cooperation is a unique case due to the country's longstanding military involvement in politics, frequent coups, and institutionalized military influence over domestic affairs. In Thailand, civil-military dynamics are deeply entwined with national security, regime protection, and political control. The Royal Thai Armed Forces' (RTAF) prominent role in responding to natural disasters like the 2011 floods and tsunamis where the military provided extensive support in evacuation, infrastructure repair, and distribution of relief materials to the affected civilians with significant logistical and operational capacity suffice (see, Raymond, 2023; Chambers, 2013; and Funston, 2009).

4. CHALLENGES FACING CIMIC

Despite the significance of CIMIC for effective operations in conflict zones, peacekeeping missions, and disaster relief, it nonetheless faces several challenges that can hinder its success. These challenges arise from differences in mandates, operational cultures, objectives, and resource capacities between military and civilian actors. First, there is a challenge of divergent mandates and objectives placing military goals in contrast to the humanitarian goals. This challenge arose most times because while militaries often operate with security or political mandates, humanitarian and development actors prioritize neutrality, impartiality, and needs-based aid. Most times, this divergence can lead to tension or mistrust, especially in complex emergencies. This happened in Afghanistan, where civilian aid agencies were reluctant to collaborate with NATO forces due to concerns about losing their neutrality in a conflict zone.

Second, there is a challenge of lack of mutual understanding and trust. This happens when both civilian and military actors lack awareness of each other's roles and operational cultures. This usually results in miscommunication, duplication of efforts, or even conflict over priorities. Third, there is a challenge of politicization and perception issues. Here, civilian organizations working with militaries may be perceived as partial or aligned with political or military agendas thereby compromising their access and credibility. In some cases, locals may become suspicious of humanitarian actors and see them as collaborators of the soldiers.

Furthermore, there is usually a problem of coordination and communication gaps due to absence of established coordination mechanisms or information-sharing platforms, which can hinder timely decision-making and effective joint planning. Also, different reporting systems, timelines, and command structures complicate coordination. Fifth, there is issue of resource and capacity imbalances. This happens when militaries often have superior logistics, funding, and infrastructure compared to civilian actors. Such imbalance can create dependency or resentment, and civilians may feel overshadowed or co-opted by military presence. The sixth point is the operational security concerns. While the military actors prioritize force protection that can restrict movement or access for civilian actors in high-risk areas, aid organizations may avoid military convoys to preserve their neutral status, thus, limiting CIMIC effectiveness.

Lastly, there are cultural and organizational differences where the military's hierarchical, mission-focused culture often contrasts with the flexible, participatory approaches of civilian organizations and create friction in joint operations or shared spaces like coordination centers among others (Winslow, 1998; UN OCHA, 2008).

5. CONCLUSION

The international community's security perception redefinition, coupled with the changed nature of conflicts and the evolution in crisis intervention, initiated a confounding of the traditional functions of the military and humanitarian actors. In particular, problems become apparent when the international military forces do not or are not able to restrict their tasks to their core competency of security-related issues. However, there is a broad consensus that the military can effectively contribute to securing peace. As claimed by Dag Hammerskjöld, the former UN Secretary General, in 1953, as the UN was embarking on its first generation of peacekeeping, "Peacekeeping is not a job for soldiers, but only soldiers can do it."

Today, globally, peacekeeping has become an integral part of the military profession. The realization has moved closer to the statement given by Lieutenant Colonel P. E. Korström, that "Peacekeeping is a job for soldiers, but soldiers alone cannot do it." The conceptions of peacekeeping and civil-military cooperation have changed fundamentally since the end of the Cold War, and a consolidation is not likely to occur in the foreseeable future. Within the different nation militaries, there are diverse

interpretations of CIMIC that exist. CIMIC contributes to the enhancement of mutual understandings between military and civilian components and is an essential tool faced with a third and possibly a fourth generation of peacekeeping. Concluding, to seamlessly achieve the best global practices for CIMIC, there is a need to find ways to improve both the cooperation and coordination activities in peacekeeping operations by the military and civilian components so as to effectively achieve the ultimate goal of peacebuilding efforts in conflict environments and situations around the world.

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